

THE ROLE OF THE GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *This article discusses the importance of using games in teaching English. Games make classes interesting and exciting. They help improve the vocabulary of the language of students. Also games develop memory, agility, resourcefulness. The article substantiates the role of games in teaching English.*

Keywords: *Teaching foreign language, interactive methods, communicating skills, different games, learner's vocabulary, teaching materials, vocabulary, structure explanations and drills, native language, pedagogical value.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается важность использования игр в обучении английскому языку. Игры делают занятия интересными и увлекательными. Они помогают улучшить словарный запас языка учащихся. Также игры развивают память, ловкость, находчивость. В статье обосновывается роль игр в обучении английскому языку.*

Ключевые слова: *обучение иностранному языку, интерактивные методы, коммуникативные навыки, различные игры, словарный запас учащихся, учебные материалы, словарный запас, объяснения структуры и упражнения, родной язык, педагогическая ценность.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatishda o'yinlardan foydalanish muhimligi muhokama qilinadi. O'yinlar darslarni qiziqarli qiladi. Ular o'quvchilar tilining so'z boyligini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, o'yinlar xotirani, chaqqonlikni, topqirlikni rivojlantiradi. Maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatishda o'yinlarning roli asoslanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Chet tilini o'rgatish, interfaol usullar, muloqot ko'nikmalari, turli o'yinlar, o'quvchining lug'at boyligi, o'quv materiallari, lug'at, tuzilmaviy tushuntirish va mashqlar, ona tili, pedagogik qadriyat.*

INTRODUCTION

It is commonly believed that in teaching foreign language the role of interactive methods is very important. Because it makes the learners to motivate and keep their interests whole lessons Interactive methods include games, songs, poems, activities. Also games improve the learner's vocabulary building skills. Vietnamese pupils learn vocabulary passively several factors. First, they consider the teacher's explanation for meaning or definition pronunciation, spelling and grammatical functions are boring. In this case language learners have nothing to do in a vocabulary learning section but to listen to their teacher. Second, children only think of vocabulary learning as knowing the primary meaning of new words. Third, pupils usually only acquire new vocabulary through new words in their textbooks or when given by teachers during classroom lessons. For example, learners find many words in a text and then ask the teacher to explain the meanings and usages Fourth, many learners don't want to take risks in applying what they have learnt. In summary games are useful and effective that would be applied in vocabulary classes. Teaching lessons through activities requires convenient storage and easy retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. Ideally you should have a room large enough. If you keep your filing cabinet to the right or left of your desk, you will be able to reach at bottom three drawers without moving your chair. With small classes do well in unshaped formation or horseshoe. Very large classes might work in groupings of four, six or a double horseshoe. Try different arrangements to see what suits you and your pupils. Some suggestions for bulletin boards include: scenes of pupil's native country and customs, the four seasons, manners, health, holidays, safety, school rules and so on.

Culturally rich resources can easily be used in language classrooms. Songs offer a change from routine classroom activities. Songs also give new insights into the target culture. Like songs, poems exaggerate the rhythmic nature of the language. If a poem that exemplifies a particular structure is also a good poem, it engages the eye, the ear and tongue simultaneously while also stimulating and moving us. Using these interactive methods in English lessons more useful and meaningful, also it is easy may to teach new words and word combinations, theme, culture and etc. Now we will see one by one of these methods. There are many ways to teach ESL to children but one of the most exciting and rewarding ways to do it is by using English games. We learned to understand and speak our first language by hearing and using it in natural situations. This is the most effective and interesting way to learn the second language as well. The experts advise that language teachers to spend most of the classroom time on activities that faster natural acquisition

rather than on formal vocabulary and structure explanations and drills. Before learning the second language we should know our first language well. Because if we know our native language well we can easily learn the second language. Teaching English language through activities and games require a convenient storage and easily retrieval of materials, objects, pictures, toys, games, conversation pieces and other props. Ideally, we should have a room larger for an audio center, a quiet work center and an activity center. But if you are traveling teacher or teach in a broom closet, some where you should have a desk, closet, bookshelves and a filing cabinet at your disposal. They all help the pupils to learn the language more excellent clearer and they make pupils to motivate. English games not only engage the children, but also through play and most of the time the pupils don't know they are learning until the time comes to show their knowledge. If truly is possible and necessary to create a classroom where he children not only learn also, they may enjoy their time there. «There are many reasons for using games. Games are not just time filling activities. But they have a great educational value». Most language games make the learners to use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. W. R. Lee says that games should be treated as central, not peripheral to the foreign language teaching program. A similar opinion is expressed by Richard Amato, who believes games to be fun, but warns against overlooking their pedagogical value, particularly in foreign language teaching. We know that there are many advantages of using games. Games provide a less threatening environment. Besides games make passive pupils active in learning process by providing a challenging environment. In addition, games provide language practice in various skills, speaking, listening, reading and writing. Although our games were short activities and were applied to create a relaxed, pleasant learning atmosphere, in the classroom, we wanted games to be more just fun. Games should also promote learning and pupils' vocabulary as well. Therefore, it is important to progress in learning vocabulary through games. Games are often used as short warm-up activities or when there is some time left at the end of a lesson. Rixon suggests that games are used at all stages of the lesson, provided that they are well-chosen. We know that, sometimes children usually full bored in vocabulary lessons, because they have not changed their learning habits, such as writing words on paper, trying to learn by heart or learning passively through the teacher's explanations. To help children find language classes, especially vocabulary lessons more from games, we conducted action research to find the answers to the question. The research shows they are effective in helping children to improve their vocabulary

building skills. In learning a foreign language vocabulary plays an important role. It is one element that links the four skills of speaking, listening, reading and writing, all together. In order to communicate well in foreign language children should know how to use them accurately. When we teach English language through activities, the focus of the lesson is on the object of the activity not on English. We will be using natural whole language whatever is needed- for explaining and participating in the game, craft, trick or other project. This will provide listening, practice through a wide range of structures and vocabulary and speaking practice at whatever level the pupils can perform, whether it will be single words, short phrases, simple sentences or complex discourse. In what order should we select activities? This will depend a great deal on the age, abilities, and needs of your class as well as the season of the year, facilities and equipment of your disposal. Helping this equipment your lesson become more effective.

Games and problem solving activities can be used for all levels. Games and problem solving activities, which are task-based and have a purpose beyond the production of correct speech, are the examples of the most preferable communicative activities. Such activities highlight not only the competence but also the performance of the learners. Both games and problem solving activities have a goal. Games are organized according to the rules and they are funny. Most games require choral responses or group works, problem solving activities, require individual response and creative solutions. Games and problem solving activities are generally used after the presentation, in the practice part, because such communication – five tasks can only be handled after mastering sufficient grammar and lexical points. Through well-planned games, learners can practice and internalize vocabulary, grammar and structure extensively. By regarding the proficiency, age and experience of the learners, appropriate activities might be applied successfully. In sum, games and problem solving activities provide favorable usages for extended communicative practice of grammar. They are both motivating and challenging. They encourage the learners to interact and communicate. So, these activities create a meaningful context for language use. The use of such activities both increase the cooperation and in the classroom. So far, the usage of the songs, poems, games and problem solving 163 activities are clarified. The advantages and some key points are explained. It is now more apparent that the teaching of grammar can be supported effectively, by using such resources'. Such activities are pupil's centered, hence by using them you give a chance to your pupils to express

themselves, enjoy themselves during learning and the use the reserves of their minds.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that there are many advantages of using games. Games provide a less threatening environment. Besides games make passive pupils active in learning process by providing a challenging environment. In addition, games provide language practice in various skills, speaking, listening, reading and writing. Although our games were short activities and were applied to create a relaxed, pleasant learning atmosphere, in the classroom, we wanted games to be more just fun. Games should also promote learning and pupils' vocabulary as well.

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